

Immortality of caste in Buddhism and Jainism

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Abstract:

The presence of Caste System in the Jain and Buddhist community has often been seen as a problem by the observers and scholars. Jainism as well as Buddhism religion as such does not recognise the castes in the community. Some Scholars believes It was at later stage that the These Religions adopted casteist feature. But the seeds of Casteism was existed in both the religions from the very beginning of their establishment. Variety of factors can be related to the formation of the caste system among the Jains and Baudhs. In many respects the caste system among the Jains and Baudhs shared similarities with those of the Hindus. Yet by twentieth century certain unique and typical features emerged in These Religions. The paper will discuss this dynamics of the caste system in the Jainism and Buddhism. It has been long recognised that Buddhism and Jainism were not movements for social reform directed against the caste system, and that the Buddha's doctrine did not aim at transformation or improvement of the social conditions. Still, the Buddha's criticism of the caste system in general and of the social superiority claimed by the brahmanas is still interpreted by some to mean that the Buddha held that "all men are born equal" or that his ideal was to establish a classless society.³ We are of the view that the Buddha by his teaching unwittingly strengthened the caste system by explaining it in terms of the doctrine of karma.

Keywords: Jainism, Buddhism, Casteism, Samgha

Features of the Caste System in Buddhist Scriptures:

It seems clear that by the time the Buddhist texts were composed, the caste system had already acquired most of its essential features. In the *Madhura Sutta* of the *Majjhimanikaya* (II 4.4) and in the *Assalayana Sutta* of *Majjhima* (II 5.3), the brahmanas claim to be of superior caste (*brdmano settho venno*) and the rest are of inferior caste (*hino anno vanno*) the *brahmanas* claim to have fair complexion (*sukko vanno*), while others are dark (*kanho*); the *brahmanas* are pure (*sujjhanti*), while *non-brahmanas* are not. The purity of caste blood was highly prized and was a bar to inter-caste marriages. In the *Canki Sutta* of the *Majjhima* (II 5.5), one of the grounds on which Canki is dissuaded from going to the Buddha is that Canki, both on his father's and mother's side, is of pure descent back through seven successive generations, without break or blemish in his caste lineage (*jati vadana*). Canki replies that Gotama is also of pure descent for seven generations both on the mother's and father's sides.

The *Ambattha Sutta* (iii) of the *Dighanidya* (I 92-93) records the fear, entertained by the exiled children of Okkaka, a King of the Sakyas, of caste impurity (*jati sambheda bhaya*) that may lead to marriage between brothers and sisters (*sakahi bhaginihi saddhim samvasam kappenti*). There is also a reference to denial of seat (*dsana*) or water (*uddakam*) (*ibid.* III 98) to a person excommunicated from the caste group. In modern Indian parlance, it means that there can be no sharing of *hookah* (smoking bubble) and water with the person who is expelled from the caste.

In the story of Vidudabha contained in the *Dhammapada Atthakatha* (4.3), King Pasenadi of Kosala is incensed at being tricked by Mahanama, King of the Sakyas, who has given him in marriage a daughter, advertised as a pure ksatriya blood, but actually Vasabhakhattiya, born from a slave girl. When Pasenadi discovers this deception, he degrades his queen and her son, Vidudabha, to the status of slaves. The Buddha, the kinsman of the Sakyas, pacifies Pasenadi by emphasising to him that the family of the mother does not matter; "it is the family (*gotra*) of the father that affords the only true measure of social position." Thus, the Buddha seems to have accepted the principle of blood purity as the determinant of social superiority.

The *Esukari Sutta* of the *Majjhima* (II 5.6) indicates that occupations were linked to castes, and that occupational mobility across caste divisions was frowned upon. The *sutta* states that a member of the higher caste could not serve a member of the lower caste: a brahmana may be served by members of all the castes; a ksatriya (*khattiyya*) by a ksatriya, vaisya (*vessa*) or sudra (*sudda*), a vaisya by a vaisya or sudra; and a sudra by a sudra only. At *Majjhima* II 180, a brahmana maintains that it is blameable conduct for anyone to desert his vocation for something else: *bhikkhacariyam ca pana brahmano sandhanam atimannamano akiccakari hoti, gopo va adinnam ddivamano ti*: by discarding alms begging, a brahmana fails to fulfil his duty or obligations, and is like a guardian who takes what is not given to him. The same

is true of a ksatriya, vaisya or sudra, who abandons the duties prescribed for his caste.

This is in consonance with the teaching of the *Bhagavadgita* which enjoins (4.13, 18.41—47) performance of *varra-karma* as the most important means for attainment of *siddhi*, liberation. T.W. Rhys Davids, in *Buddhist India* adduces considerable evidence from the *Jatakas* to establish that caste-based occupational rigidity had ceased to exist and that there were marriages between members of higher and lower castes (including sudras) that did not lead to loss of caste. So far as the question of occupational flexibility is concerned, the successful assault on *yajna-karma*, religious sacrifices, by Buddhism and Jainism, and consequent occupational loss to the brahmanas would have driven them to take up professions that in theory were the monopoly of other castes.

The Buddha's Attitude Toward Caste:

The Buddha's reactions to these features of the caste system do not indicate that he repudiated or condemned the caste system. In the *Madhura Sutta* of the *Majjhima* (II 85), he maintains that all four castes are equal: *ime cattaro vanna samasamahonti*; and describes the brahmanas' claim to superiority as an empty boast (*ghoso*). In the *Assaldyana Sutta* of the *Majjhima* (II 149) and the *Madhura Sutta, Majjhima* II 87, the Buddha refutes the claim of higher castes to superiority—but on metaphysical grounds: after death, they shall be reborn in accordance with their karmas and not in accordance with their caste (*jati*): "a man who is a murderer or a thief or a fornicator, or a liar, or a slanderer, or of violent speech or rattles or covets or is malevolent or holds wrong views, he will, after death at body's dissolution pass to the state of misery and woe, whether he be a brahmana, a ksatriya, a vaisya or a Sudra." In *Jataka* no. 498, the origin of *candlas*, described as the lowest race and the meanest of men, is traced to karma: "When all our deeds were ripe as guerdon meet, we both as young *candalas* had our birth" (*sakehi kammehi supapekhi candala gabbhe avasimha pubbe*). Regarding the concept of the purity of caste blood, in the *Assalayana Sutta* of the *Majjhima* (II 154), the Buddha maintains that all castes are of equal purity: *catu vannim suddhim paccagato*. But he attacks the claims of the caste conscious brahmana to social superiority on the ground that his purity of blood might be suspect: *jananti pana . . . ya janimatu mata yava sattama mata mahayuga brahmanam yeva agamasi no abrahmana*: "Do you know for certain that your mother's mother and your grandmother for seven generations had intercourse with brahmanas only and never with non-brahmanas?" The Buddha goes on to repeat the same for the father's side (*sattampita mahayugd*). (*ibid* II 156) In the *Ambaitha Sutta* of *Dighanikaya* III, the Buddha recognises the caste-superiority of ksatriyas over

brahmanas by pointing out that the ksatriyas do not admit a child born of *ananuloma*, or *pratiloma* marriage into their caste, even though the mother or father might be a ksatriya and the other a brahmana. Such a child was admitted to the brahmana caste.

The Buddha therefore concludes that when one compares women with women (*itthiya va itthim*) or men with men (*purisena va purisam*), the ksatriyas are superior (*settho*) to the brahmanas, who are lower (*hina*). The Buddha avers: *khattiyo parama nihinatam patto hoti*, even when a ksatriya is fallen in the deepest degradation, *khattiyo va settha hino brahmano*, the ksatriya is superior, brahmana inferior. The Buddha quotes Sanam Kumara, a Brahma god, to the effect that the ksatriya is the best among those who believe in caste lineage (*gotra*): *khattiyo settho jani tasmin ye gotta patisarino*.

Again, in the *Esukdri Sutta*, the Buddha's reaction to occupational restrictions and rigidity in relation to various castes is equivocal; all that he emphasises is that "if the service makes a man bad and not good, it should not be rendered but if it makes him better and not bad, then it should be rendered." He emphasises: "I assert that *uccakullna*, high class family, does not enter into a man's being either good or bad, nor do good looks or wealth, for you will find a man of noble birth who is a murderer, a thief, a fornicator; therefore I assert that noble birth does not make a good man . . ." In other words, the Buddha recognises the existence of the caste system and only emphasises that it is the moral conduct of a person and not his caste that determines whether he is good or bad. This is saying the obvious; it is no challenge to the caste system. There is direct evidence in the *suttas* that the Buddha recognised caste distinctions. In the *Kannakattala Sutta* of *Majjhima* 4.10 (II 128-129), the Buddha, addressing Pasenadi, observes that there are four castes, *khattiyas, brahmanas, vessas* and *suddas*. "Among these four castes . . . two are pointed to as chief, the nobles (*khattiya*) and the brahmanas, that is to say, in the way of addressing them, rising up from one's seat for them, saluting them with joined palms and rendering them service." Again, Buddhas take birth only in two castes, ksatriya and brahmana. The Buddha clarifies that from the point of view of causality (*heturupam*) there is no distinction or difference in a future state between the castes provided they strive equally for freedom or the end of sorrow. Again in the *Esukari Sutta*

{*Majjhima* II 181), a person's birth in a particular family of known parentage on the father's and mother's side is what determines his caste designation:

poranam—pan'assa mata pettikam kulavarhsam [khattiya, brahmana, etc.] anussarato yatha yatth'

evamattabhavassa abhinibbati hoti, ten ten' eva sankham gacchati.

From the *Assalayana Sutta (Majjhima II 149)* it is evident that the Buddha was also aware that among the Yonas and Kambojas, those outside the aryan fold, there were only two classes, nobles and slaves, but that their classes and occupations were interchangeable:

yona kambojesu dveva vanna ayyo c'eva daso ca; ayyo hutva daso hoti daso hutva ayyo hoti. The Buddha never advocated this class structure as a first step to a casteless society. Regarding the participation of sudras and outcastes in religious life, it is significant that the Buddha's sermons are addressed to ksatriyas, brahmanas, *grhapatis* (respectable householders) and *sramanas* or their *parisds* (assemblies). In the *Kutadanta Sutta (Dighanikdya V 136)* only the ksatriyas, brahmanas and householders are invited to attend the great *yajna (homam)* organised by the king—a *yajna* approved by the Buddha. At *Anguttaranikdya III 363*, the Buddha describes the goals in life of the three upper castes and makes no mention of the goals of the sudras and *pancamas*. In other words, the Buddha ignored the Sudras and outcastes while encouraging religious life among the people. There is also no evidence that the Buddha ever denounced the discriminatory caste system based penal laws of the *Dharmasdstas*. In fact, the Buddhist texts do not even show any awareness of such discrimination.

Buddhist and Jainism Monks and the Caste System:

Both Buddhism and Jainism led to the creation of another class outside the lay social system: the *bhikkhus* of the Buddhists, the *sadhhus and yatis* of the Jainas, and the *parivrajakas* and *sadhhus* of the Brahmanical faith. They were a class *sui generis*, not bound by the caste restrictions, who had renounced lay life for good, irrevocably. Unlike outcastes, they commanded the respect of all the lay castes. This group and this group alone the Buddha had proclaimed free from caste distinctions: it was casteless. In the *Cullavagga* of the *Vinaya Pitaka (IX I. 4)* the Buddha says, "just as . . . all the great rivers namely Gariga, Yamuna, Aicravati, Sarabhu, Mahl, when they reach the great ocean, lose their former names and differences and are denominated as the great ocean, even so . . . these four castes (*vanna*) ksatriyas, brahmanas, vaisyas, Sudras, when they go forth from the household to houseless life under the doctrine and discipline (*dhamma vinaye*), lose their former family names (*namagottani*) and are denominated as *samana*" In the *Anguttaranikdya (III 240)*, this is graphically represented by a dream of Gotama in which four birds of four different colours (*nana vanna*) fall at his feet and become entirely white (*sabbaseta*),

symbolising abandonment of castes by those laymen who give up the household life and, join the sangha. Thus, in the *Ambattha Sutta (Digha III 2.1)*, the Buddha emphasises that "there is not. . . in the highest perfection of knowledge and virtue, any talk of caste (*jativddo*) or of family (*gotta-vado*) In the *Madhura Sutta (Majjhima 84)*, it is emphasised that whosoever renounces household life and joins the order of monks—be he a brahmana, ksatriya, vaishya or Sudra—and abstains from stealing, falsehood, etc., and observes the good law, would be entitled to respect and honour irrespective of his caste prior to renunciation. The *Uddalakajataka*, no. 487 (307), and *Nimijataka*, no. 541 (101), make it clear that caste ceases to have relevance when a person attains sainthood.

On the other hand, slaves and debtors were not admitted to the sangha unless the slaves had been freed by their masters and the debtors had discharged their debts. This could only restrict severely any scope for breakdown of the caste system via the samgha.

Caste System among the Jainism:

It is at the later stage that the Jain community adopted this feature of socio-economic and ideological life of India and gradually castes, which existed in Hinduism, emerged in Jainism, too. Variety of factors can be related to the formation of the caste system among the Jains. The mass conversion of Hindus to Jainism was one of the significant reasons. The overwhelming and dominant influence of Hinduism was difficult to escape from. As a small number of Jains had to live among the non-Jains, in particularly among the Hindus, the acceptance of Hindu practices became natural and obvious. Again, regional variations and traditions contributed to, a greater extent, to the formation of the castes in Jainism. The origin of many of the Jain castes can be traced to 'particular' place. In most cases the Jain castes originated from the urban background. They were named after the places of their origin. Śrīmālīs were so called as they came from Srimala; Osavāls from Osia and so on.

With this historical background the caste system of the Jains conceptually developed. For the fact that the Jains as a community originated from different backgrounds, they organised themselves into differing groups known as Jati or naat. The Jain caste system is evolved in the sense that each individual is regarded as belonging to a social group. Some of the features of the caste system of the Jains are as follows:

- By twentieth century the Jains stood as caste-bound community. The castes became significant component of the Jain community.
- One finds the existence of Jain castes wherein all the members of the caste are Jains.

- At the same time there have been Jain divisions of several Hindu castes. To illustrate there are Agravālas, Śrīmālīs, Porvāḍas etc. both among Hindus and Jains.

- Many of the castes in the Jain community are spread over a wide area. They are found in large number in cities like Mumbai, Calcutta, Delhi, and Nagpur.

- There are different regions where different Jain castes have been mainly concentrated. Śrīmālīs are found mainly in Gujarat, Osavāls in Gujarat and Rajasthan and so on. Many of these Jain castes have their national and state associations. These organisations conduct their caste-journals, get their caste-histories published and hold conferences at regular intervals. Thus, the caste sentiments and loyalties are strengthened and preserved.

Jains & Hindus:

The caste system of the Jains differed in many respects from those of the Hindus.

- The caste system among the Jains is a social and not religious institution. The system neither in the past nor in the present sanctioned by the Jain religion. This is a crucial point when compared with the Hindu castes.

- The attitude of the Jainism is nonetheless is that it is one of the social practices unconnected with religion, observed by people.

- While the Jains claim to have a separate religion, they are invariably classified into the Hindu Varna system, with the appellation 'Bania' often suffixed to their community name.

- One of the important features of caste system of the Hindus is the hierarchy of the castes. The Hindu castes have been arranged in an order of social precedence with Brahmins as the head of the hierarchy. The highest position accorded to the Brahmins is the important basis of the Caste organisation of Hindu society. Even the reformist movements of the twentieth century largely aimed to bring better status and treatment to the lower strata than to reject the hierarchy or the privileged positions. On the other hand in spite of the existence of the numerous castes in the Jain community, hardly prominent position is assigned to any caste. All castes are treated on equal footing and there is no differentiation as regard to social prestige. There is prevalence of a feeling of superiority among some Jain castes. They consider themselves superior over other castes or particular divisions of a caste. This may be due to differences in moral standards, social practices, customs and manners for e.g. the castes which do not allow widow remarriage consider themselves as superior to those which allow and practice widow remarriage. The division of Osavāls in Visa and Dasa is traced to this practice. Yet on the whole there is lack of caste hierarchy on the basis of social precedence in the Jain community.

Jainism has rejected the traditional idea of society being structured around purity and impurity. Implied from this, there is no ban on dining with any other member of the Jain community irrespective of his or her caste. Untouchability practically does not exist amongst Jains. No restrictions exist on social intercourse between different Jain castes. This may be due to the uniformity of practice in matters of diet. Hence differences of social nature do not operate as a bar. No more caste prescriptions play a vital role in the life of the Jains. It would not be wrong to say that today the prime determinant for Jain caste ranking is essentially economic status.

Caste as religious division:

Caste was not considered as part of the cosmic order in Jainism. The doctrinal claim of a divine origin of the castes was not adhered to. It has never been seen as a religious division for e.g. Jain sects do not reject or obstruct the recruitment to asceticism on the grounds of the caste. The caste as sociopolitical distinction did not face great objection but has not been accepted valid in the religious domain. There is absence of caste restrictions in religious domain. However, some practices did prevail. Many of the Jain castes have Visa and Dasa subdivisions. Religious disabilities were imposed on Dasa persons. They could not worship in temples at all.

Conclusion:

The classification as has been prevalent in the society was worth based and not the one based on birth as is prevalent in the present day society of India. The caste system slowly but systematically took its root in the Indian society with social discrimination as its dangerous byproduct. The Caste system became hereditary ensuing its present day characteristics over the changes that occurred over the past 1000 years. The major reason for such a diversion from the concept of 'Theory of three Varnas' of the Rig Vedic period into the 'Chaturvarna system' as explained by Dr. B.R. Ambedkar was due to constant aggression between the kings [sudras] and the priestly class [brahmins] as in some of the Sudra kingdoms, the Brahmins underwent tyrannies. The Brahmanas in vengeance decided to refuse to consecrate the Sudras with sacred thread which led to slow degradation of the social status of the Sudras. The Sudras were thereafter, relegated to the deplorable condition and slowly the 'class' changed into the 'fourth caste' in the Caste system. the Jains converted the caste system into what was acceptable and fitting in the context of their tradition. The role of theistic creation was eliminated, and the existence of the caste system on the basis of conduct, rather than of some irrevocable cosmic order was justifiably accepted. The research also concludes that the Buddhism and Jainism[especially the former one]

that evolved as a result of social evils also played its part in worsening the already deplorable condition of the lowest caste despite their fleshy claims of equality. Infact, few scholars are of the opinion that the forced drive for vegetarianism as was done by the two faiths led to its adoption in the vedic society too which reinforced the dormant untouchability. These faiths also played their part for making social groups untouchable in the manner that strong moralist tendencies and blind emphasis on non-violence lead to occupations like dancers, hunters, fishermen and butchers into defiled professions which propogated exactly opposite of what was envisioned in the pre-modern times the heredity or family was a unit for successfully instating skills that would run the society smoothly. At the end, the later Vedic Religion also played its part in slowly building up the caste system. The logical conclusion for such a state of development for later vedic religion is the ocean of scriptures which supported the plurality and diversity of ideas expressed by diverse people who wrote the literature and scriptures in later vedic age which lead to eclectic conflicting and incoherent ideas in the compilations of that period.

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3. A.K. Warder, *Indian Buddhism* (Delhi, 1980), p. 164, 169.
4. Likewise in the *Sonadanda Sutta* of the *Dighanikaya* 4.120.21, in *Vdsefiha Sutta* (98) of the *Majjhima* (II 5.8) and in the *Sarhyuttanikaya* (115), the brahmanas claim that what made a brahmana was pure descent on both the parental sides right back through seven successive generations of ancestors with no break or blemish in the lineage. The *Satapatha Brahmana* (1, 8.3.6) prohibits marriage among blood relations up to the 3rd or 4th degree. According to *Kalpasutra* 17, Jaina arhats, etc., are born in families of pure descent on both sides (*visuddhajati kulavansesu*).
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8. *The Jdtakas, ibid.*, vol.III, p. 154. In the *Brhadhranyaka XJpanisad* (VI 4.13) it is laid down that a Sudra should not touch a married woman undergoing periodic impurity (menstruation).

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